

Archaeological Surveys in India and Archaeological Survey of India

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Abstract

Archaeological Surveys in India and Archaeological Survey of India are not one and the same. The former started by the government in the first half of the nineteenth century, whereas the latter was established in 1871.

Officers of Colonial government, baffled by the rich cultural heritage of great antiquity strewn all around, knew its great value and started collecting them. Their searches associated with documentation and study form an important phase in the development of archaeology in India. History of this phase, falling under the period termed as modern history, perhaps did not engage most archaeologists and heritage enthusiasts. What was written and printed by some early writers was more or less accepted and faithfully reproduced by others. Some differing views also surfaced time to time but no consensus based on facts and records is seen. This paper attempts to look into the past through available records on the matter and try to find out the probable cause for the confusion about the establishment of the Archaeological Survey of India, a 150 year old central organization with a long and eventful history.

Key Words: Archaeological surveys in India, Archaeological Survey of India, History of archaeology in India

India's splendor is not confined only to her physical extent, from snow covered peaks of the Himalayas to shores of the Indian Ocean, but also in its long and eventful history and rich heritage. The 'Mistress of the Eastern Seas' is extremely rich in cultural heritage and every area is strewn with archaeological remains of great antiquity. These treasures of the past, in diverse forms, attracted several British officers who explored the length and breadth of the country in search and collection of them. Of course, their documentation and study also formed a part of the scheme. These antiquaries and their works form an important phase in the development of archaeology in India.

One thing must be understood clearly that history of archaeological surveys in India is not the history of Archaeological Survey of India. Archaeological surveys were conducted time to time by different officers long before establishment of this grand old institution in the year 1871. One

such archaeological survey, which started from December 1861, was often erroneously interpreted as the beginning of the organisation.

This erroneous narrative started building up almost at the same time when the organisation was being set up. Published in 1871, *A Memoir on the Indian Surveys* tracing the history of archaeological surveys in India take its foundation back to 1860. Markham records that “it was not until 1860 that the Government of India instituted an archaeological survey, with the object of preserving ancient monuments, rendering them easy of access, obtaining correct copies of inscriptions and pieces of sculpture, and thus facilitating the studies of future antiquaries and historians”(Markham, 1871:196; 1876:263). Western style of history, which is taught in India, somehow promoted copying more than analysing facts or implementation of knowledge gained for understanding causes and effects. Those trained in such traditions readily, more or less, accepted whatever was written, printed rather, and the same was frequently repeated by several other authors. Some others tried to do something different and tried to establish with other events which took place at a later date (Ghosh, 1953: 1).

Different Dates

Most archaeologists in India are mainly fascinated with digging of archaeological sites and remains, study and documentation of material evidence of past and their interpretation or reinterpretation, most of the time. Like many historians, history of archaeology hardly interests them. As a result, very few serious researches are seen on these aspects of history. A glance on some related works in the past would suggest that there was no consensus on the issue.

Markham (1871: 196) in his *Memoir on the Indian Surveys* set 1860 as the beginning of archaeological surveys in India. At the same time, Alexander Cunningham (1871) published his previous reports in a series which he started as the Director-General of Archaeology. Inclusion of report for the year 1861-62 in the first volume seemed to authenticate the date given by Markham which created a false impression. He undoubtedly explored several important places and thoroughly documented them, for about fifteen years. The remaining period of the nineteenth century, after Alexander Cunningham relinquished his office in 1885, was not very eventful.

In the beginning of the twentieth century, when the Archaeological Survey of India was put on firm footing, John Marshall started a new series of publications. In his introduction, in the first volume for the year 1902-03, he too traced the brief history. He also adhered to the established timeline and wrote “The history of the Archaeological Department may be said to open with the appointment in 1862 of Major General Sir Alexander Cunningham to be “Director of Archaeology” (Marshall, 1904: 3). What established by Marshall, continued unaltered and no attempt was made thereafter to research on this aspect in British India.

Fifty years later, in 1952, the Archaeological Survey of India celebrated “fifty years” of its “continued existence”. In the *Bulletin of the Archaeological Survey of India*, A. Ghosh (1953: 1) writes “The Archaeological Survey of India as a Central organization completed fifty years of its continued existence in 1952, to be precise on the 21st February”. In a way, the (firm) foundation

of organization was thus considered from the joining of John Marshall as the Director-General of the Archaeological Survey of India.

Only after nine years, in 1961, the Archaeological Survey of India celebrated the centenary of her foundation. On this occasion, in the same bulletin of the organization, it was recorded that “In December this year (1961) we are celebrating the Centenary of the Survey” (Ghosh, 1961: 1). Celebration of the centenary within a decade from celebrating fifty-years was definitely going to create some confusion. Organizers, therefore, further clarified by mentioning “That an organization only fifty years old in 1952 should now become a centennial may seem to be a jugglery to many . . . “. Here the date was reverted to earlier one mentioning clearly that “the origin of the Survey dates back to 1861, which, in turn, would explain its Centenary Celebration in 1961” (Ghosh, 1961: 1). Once accepted by the organization, in Independent India, no further analysis was considered necessary and in 2011, the Archaeological Survey of India celebrated 150 years of its foundation on a grand scale (Sengupta and Lambah, 2012).

What is discussed above were official decisions based on official records. But actually, what date should be considered foundation of the organization still remains a question for archaeologists, historians and researchers as different dates kept cropping up time to time in different publications now and then.

A booklet published on the Institute of Archaeology records “the Archaeological Survey of India as a central organization was established on 21st February, 1902”. Very recently, in 2013, Guidelines for ASI Museums (2013: 2) prepared jointly by Archaeological Survey of India, J Paul Getty Trust, U.S.A., British Museum U.K. and National Culture Fund, also mention John Marshall as the “first Director General of ASI”.

Thus it is clear that still there is no unanimity on the date of establishment of the Archaeological Survey of India, and hence it is necessary to re-examine and analyse available documents afresh to arrive on some logical and acceptable conclusion.

Many Archaeological Surveys

Whenever there are discussions on systematic or state funded surveys for archaeological purposes, generally one goes back to the 1860's when Alexander Cunningham carried out explorations in northern part of the country. But neither was Cunningham the only British officer to get appointed by the government for conducting archaeological survey nor was such appointment made for the first time. Several such appointments were made in the past where British Officers, generally army officers who were good at preparing sketches, drawings and carrying out documentation accurately, were appointed on such special duties.

Active interest of State in Indian monuments can be traced back to 1844 when Court of Directors recommended to the Government of India to employ some of the talented officers (Roy, 1953: 9). Lord Hardinge recommended entrusting such works to the “officers possessing habit of

research and knowledge of Indian antiquities". Captain Markham Kittoe was appointed as 'Archaeological Enquirer' in the North-West Provinces to conduct operations in Bihar and Banaras (Roy, 1953: 9-10). While on archaeological duty he conducted excavations at Sarnath near Benares (Markham, 1871:186).

Another such officer who was appointed for archaeology related work was Captain Gill. Hewas appointed "to copy the paintings in Ajanta and the Ghat caves and the setting up of the Bombay cave-temple commission" (Roy, 1953: 10). On the recommendation of Bombay Cave-temple Commission, "Lt. Brett was commissioned in 1851 to take impressions of the cave-inscriptions" (Roy, 1953: 10).

A young officer who contributed significantly was F.C. Maisey. On the orders of Lieutenant-Governor of the North-West Provinces he "prepared an illustrated account of Hindu antiquities of Kalinjar in Bundelkhand" (Maisey, 1892: 1).

In 1849 he was "employed under the Government of India, in archaeological work in Upper Betwa Districts of Central India." He was selected for this "special duty" on the recommendation of Lieutenant-Governor of the North-West Provinces (Maisey, 1892: 1). He meticulously measured the monuments and prepared drawings and copies of sculptures. Detailed account of his work was finally published in 1892. It is therefore evident that several British officers were appointed in different parts of the country, on various archaeological duties, time to time.

Generalisation has broad applications in many disciplines. But when it is done unmindfully, over generalisation creates serious confusion in history. As mentioned above it is necessary to understand difference in 'archaeological surveys in India' and 'Archaeological Survey of India'. There cannot be any doubt that both are two different things, and hence should not be mixed together. With this clear understanding let us now examine the available records and find out where the mistake could have been made.

Cunningham as Archaeological Surveyor

A careful study of records make it clear that Colonel A. Cunningham had submitted a proposal to the Governor General in November 1861 at Allahabad, "regarding an investigation of the archaeological remains of Upper India" (Cunningham, 1871: i). Although, developments immediately after submitting the proposal and the beginning of the work are not that clear but, a scrutiny of available records suggests that Lord Canning approved the proposal immediately and asked him to start his survey. Cunningham in his own report gives two different dates for beginning his survey (Cunningham, 1871: i, XLI).

This matter was minute din the Council on 22 January and the order was issued on 31 Jan 1862 appointing him as the Archaeological Surveyor from last month. There is no doubt that the proposal was submitted in November 1861 at Allahabad and work started soon after that. According to the order issued on 31 Jan 1862 he was appointed from December 1861. Due to his appointment from retrospective date, different dates are often referred by different scholars in

their writings. It is beyond doubt that Colonel Alexander Cunningham was appointed as the Archaeological Surveyor from December 1861 and hence beginning of his project of archaeological survey of upper India officially started from 1st Dec 1861. “The year 1861-62 was the first of General Cunningham” operations as archaeological surveyor (Markham, 1871: 196).

With his proposal, he had also submitted a plan of work, and he more or less followed it. The survey was initially approved for two years (Cunningham, 1871: iii). The Journal of Asiatic Society also clearly mentioned that “The President informed the meeting of the appointment by Government of Colonel A. Cunningham on an Archaeological Mission which might be expected to occupy him for the next two years and in the course of which the Colonel intended to explore the interesting district of Behar” (Dutt, 1862: 422).

“Cunningham was given a salary of Rs. 450 with a field-allowance of Rs. 250 and a share in the antiquities to be discovered by him” (Roy, 1953: 10). During his appointment as Archaeological Surveyor, it was also clearly minuted that there is going to be no expenditure in the future thus it is clear that the Government had no plans to continue it (Cunningham, 1871: ii).

This survey continued for four seasons, i.e. from 1861-62 to 1864-65. Field surveys were carried out in winter season followed by preparation of reports during summer and rainy season. The reports which he submitted to the Government were communicated to the Asiatic Society, which published them in their journal also. “Lord Lawrence abolished the appointment of Archaeological Surveyor” (Markham, 1878:265). Roy (1953: 11) records that Cunningham conducted his surveys from November 1861 to January 1865.

In 1868 Lieutenant H.H. Cole was appointed to conduct archaeological survey in the North-West Province (Markham, 1871: 199; 1878: 266).

Archaeological Survey of India

In 1870 July it was decided “that a central establishment should be formed to collect the records of former researches, to train a school of archaeologists capable of conducting local enquiries and to direct, assist, and systemize the various efforts and enquiries made by local bodies, persons as well as by the Government” (Markham, 1871:201). Since A. Cunningham was known for his previous works he was appointed as the Director General of Archaeology in India. “In 1871 General Cunningham commenced work with the aid of two assistants” (Markham, 1878: 269). He worked as Director General of the ASI from 1871 to 1885 (Bhattacharya, 2014:63).

Why This Confusion?

From the above discussions it is clear that Colonel Alexander Cunningham was appointed as the Archaeological Surveyor for a very short period for “investigation of the archaeological remains of Upper India” (Cunningham, 1871: i). The question which then arises is – Why is his short-term appointment taken as the foundation of the Archaeological Survey of India?

There can be two possible explanations. One probable reason to give an early date may be to push the date of foundation of the organisation backwards. Roy (1953: 10), in his official history projected the survey done by Cunningham as “the first archaeological survey of India”. Furthermore, a false narrative was built as “Cunningham came back to resume his interrupted task”. Another reason, which appears more probable, may be due to the annual reports published by Cunningham. We are aware that at the time of his appointment it was clearly defined that he would be submitting his reports on his works. He not only followed the plan but also submitted detailed reports on the areas he explored, monuments and sites he documented, antiquities he collected and traditions recorded. These reports were submitted annually to the government as per the condition of the appointment. Government shared them with the Asiatic Society and it published them in their Journal.

When the Archaeological Survey of India was established and Cunningham joined as the Director-General in 1871, he published these ten years old reports as volume 1 and 2 in the series which he initiated as the Director-General. Clubbing these two separate works in a single series gave a false impression to its readers that these works were also conducted by the Director-General of the Archaeological Survey of India. This appears to be the major cause of confusion and misunderstanding. Here it is noteworthy that the publication of this series was started in 1871, the year when Memoir on the Indian Surveys was also published.

Conclusion

When archaeological surveys started in India and when Archaeological Survey of India started, are two different questions having different answers. But a careful examination would suggest that both had been mixed up somewhere which created serious confusion. Study of different records and writings would give different dates at different time.

Authentic history should only be based on evidence and verifiable records. Conducting archaeological surveys by officers appointed by the government of India for this purpose cannot be considered as the beginning of the Archaeological Survey of India. It is clear that archaeological studies were conducted in India since long. British government also appointed various officers on special duty for conducting archaeological surveys or documentation of ancient and historical monuments of interest. Some such appointments include Captain Markham Kittoe, Captain Gill, Lieutenant Brett, Lieutenant F.C. Maisey, Colonel Alexander Cunningham, Lieutenant H.H. Cole, to name a few. After these several local or regional unconnected surveys, finally the British Government decided to establish a department for archaeology in the year 1870 and Major General Alexander Cunningham was appointed as the first Director General of the newly created department. He joined in February 1871 marking the beginning of the Archaeological Survey of India. The organisation continued since then and has now completed 150 years.

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